

Table 2. Rice seedling resistance to infestation by WBPH nymphs in free-choice (FC) and no-choice (NC) tests^a, IRRI greenhouse, 1983.

Variety	Resistance rating ^b											
	18 Jul			25 Jul			31 Jul			8 Aug		
	FC	NC	Difference	FC	NC	Difference	FC	NC	Difference	FC	NC	Difference
ADR52	1.0	0.9	0.1 ns	0.8	1.1	-0.3ns	0.9	0.6	0.3 ns	1.0	0.6	0.4 ns
ARC10239	1.1	1.1	0.0 ns	1.1	1.1	0.0ns	1.1	0.6	0.5 ns	1.4	1.1	0.3 ns
Colombo	1.0	1.1	-0.1 ns	1.0	1.3	-0.3ns	1.4	1.0	0.4 ns	1.1	1.0	0.1 ns
IR2035-117-3	1.0	0.7	0.3 ns	0.7	0.7	0.0 ns	0.4	0.8	-0.4 ns	0.6	0.9	-0.3 ns
Muskhan 41	1.6	1.4	0.2 ns	1.2	0.6	0.6*	0.5	1.1	-0.6*	1.0	0.9	0.1 ns
N22	1.3	2.1	-0.8**	0.9	1.9	-1.0**	0.6	2.8	-2.2**	0.8	2.2	-1.4**
N32	1.4	1.1	0.3 ns	1.1	0.7	0.4ns	0.9	0.7	0.2 ns	1.0	1.3	-0.3 ns
Podiwi A8	3.3	6.0	-2.7**	2.5	4.6	-2.1**	2.0	6.5	-4.5**	2.6	7.8	-5.2**
WC1240	0.3	0.3	0.0 ns	0.3	0.3	0.0 ns	0.2	0.3	-0.1 ns	0.4	0.7	-0.3 ns
TN1 (check)	9.0	9.0	0.0 ns	9.0	9.0	0.0 ns	9.0	9.0	0.0 ns	9.0	9.0	0.0 ns

^aAv of 5 replications. ns = not significant; *, ** significant at 5% and 1% levels. ^bScored on 0-9 scale: 0 = highly resistant, 9 = highly susceptible (1980 Standard Evaluation System for Rice).

with highly susceptible and highly resistant germplasm.

However, shortly after seedlings are infested, nymphs tend to move to the susceptible check variety, which causes imbalance in the infestation on the test varieties. If this occurs to a significant extent, the escape of a test variety may be misconstrued as genetic resistance. We compared the reliability of WBPH resistance scores obtained in free-choice and no-choice tests.

In the free-choice test, 10 varieties were sown in 40-cm-long rows, each in 60- × 45- × 10-cm wooden trays in the greenhouse. One-week-old seedlings were thinned to 15/row and covered with a fine-mesh fiberglass screen cage 55 cm long, 40 cm wide, and 50 cm

high. Each seedling was infested with five second-instar nymphs. Nymphs that settled on rice seedlings were counted at 1, 8, 24, and 48 h after infestation. Seedling damage was scored when the susceptible check TN1 died. Treatments were replicated five times and repeated four times at weekly intervals.

In the no-choice test, varieties were sown and treated as in the free-choice test, but each row of seedlings was excluded from all others by a vertical, mylar plastic partition, assuring equal exposure to insect infestation.

The initial distribution of nymphs was uniform in the free-choice test, but after 8 h or longer, nymph percentages were significantly higher on TN1 than on resistant varieties (Table 1). This

differential infestation soon after insect release created an imbalance in the infestation level of the test varieties, which helped some resistant varieties to escape damage. This shortcoming was avoided in the no-choice test.

Podiwi A8, with *wbph 4* resistance gene, was moderately resistant in the free-choice test, but susceptible in the no-choice test (Table 2). N22, with *Wbph 1*, was resistant in the free-choice test, but moderately resistant in the no-choice test.

The no-choice test, which ensures even insect distribution on the test plants, may be particularly useful in screening of hybrid seed material for inheritance studies of insect resistance. □

Reaction of rice varieties to rice ragged stunt virus (RSV) infection by three brown planthopper (BPH) biotypes

A. Parejarearn, research scholar, IRRI; D. B. Lapis, formerly senior research fellow, IRRI, now associate professor, University of the Philippines at Los Baños College of Agriculture; and H. Hibino, plant pathologist, IRRI

Recent screening data at IRRI indicated that the varieties resistant to RSV were also resistant to the vector BPH. We tested five RSV-resistant, two intermediate, and one susceptible rice varieties for resistance to three BPH biotypes and RSV infection in the greenhouse.

Varieties with resistance to BPH bio-

Reaction of 8 selected varieties to 3 BPH biotypes and RSV infection by those biotypes, IRRI.

Variety	Reaction to BPH ^a			Reaction to RSV ^b		
	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3	Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Ptb 21	S	S	S	I (35)	S (76)	S (90)
Murungakayan	R	R	S	R (26)	R (31)	I (47)
Mawee	R	R	R	R (25)	R (22)	R (24)
Balaratawee	R	MR	S	R (13)	I (48)	S (70)
Hathili	R	R	MR	R (16)	I (40)	I (46)
IR22	S	S	S	I (58)	I (58)	S (90)
IR50	R	R	MR	R (21)	I (35)	I (33)
TN1	S	S	S	S (68)	S (82)	S (90)

^aData from Entomology Department, IRRI. ^bResults of mass inoculation based on 0-30% infection = R, 31-60% infection = I, 61-100% infection = S. Figures in parentheses are percentage infection.

type 1 in the mass inoculation were less preferred by the insect and received more insect probing punctures per day. When allowed to feed on resistant varieties, biotype 1 showed shorter life-span and

low nymphal survival. Fewer nymphs were produced by adults allowed to oviposit on resistant varieties.

Seven-d-old seedlings of the test varieties were transplanted in clay pots at 20

seedlings/pot. Sixteen pots, 2/variety, were caged with viruliferous BPH of each biotype for 24 h at 5 insects/seedling. One month after inoculation, percentage of infected seedlings was recorded. Mawee, Hathili, Murungakayan, and IR50

had less RSV infection regardless of biotype. IR22 and TN1 had higher percent infection for the three biotypes (see table). For all varieties tested, reaction to RSV infection with the three BPH biotypes was similar to their reaction to the

biotypes. Results indicate that varietal reaction to RSV varies with reaction to BPH biotype vector; therefore a degree of correlation exists between BPH and RSV resistance. □

Use of a lignin-specific dye to demonstrate phloem feeding by brown planthopper (BPH)

Z. R. Khan, postdoctoral fellow, Entomology Department, IRRI; and R. C. Saxena, principal research scientist, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Nairobi, Kenya, and associate entomologist, IRRI

Microtomy of plant tissue on which the BPH has fed, qualitative and quantitative biochemical analyses of excreta, and its indicator chemical reactions have been relied upon to demonstrate phloem feeding by BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) on the rice plant. We confirmed phloem feeding by BPH on susceptible and resistant rice varieties by using safranin, a lignin-specific dye that is selectively translocated in xylem vessels and would indicate xylem feeding if the excreta were red.

Roots of 10-d-old seedlings of BPH biotype 1-susceptible TN1, and resistant ASD7 were immersed in a 0.2% aqueous solution of safranin 0 for about 6 h. After washing off the excess dye, groups of 2 or 3 treated seedlings were transferred to water-filled, small glass beakers or plastic containers in mylar cages. Ten

Filter paper discs on which honeydew of BPH biotype 1 was collected when the insect fed on susceptible TN1 and resistant ASD7 rice varieties. Bluish amino acid spots on ninhydrin-treated filter paper discs (c, d) indicate more phloem feeding on TN1, while the absence of red spots on filter paper discs (a, b) indicates lack of xylem feeding on both susceptible and resistant varieties.

newly emerged BPH biotype 1 females were then allowed to feed for 24 h on the seedlings, at the base of each of which was placed a 9-cm-diameter filter paper disc. A set of untreated seedlings were infested similarly as a control. The honeydew excreted by the hoppers dropped on the filter paper disc and was readily absorbed.

The BPH is primarily a phloem feeder because no red honeydew spots were detected on filter paper discs (Fig. 1a,b) Although the amount of BPH honeydew excreted was less on resistant ASD7 than on susceptible TN1 plants, the appearance of bluish amino acid spots indicated phloem feeding when filter paper discs from control seedlings were treated with 0.1% ninhydrin acetone solution (Fig. 1c,d). □

The BPH is primarily a phloem feeder

Electronically recorded waveforms associated with feeding behavior of green leafhopper (GLH)

Z. R. Khan, postdoctoral fellow, Entomology Department, IRRI; and R. C. Saxena, principal research scientist, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, Kenya, and associate entomologist, IRRI

We used an electronic feeding recorder to monitor GLH *Nephotettix virescens* feeding on GLH-susceptible and resistant plants.

1. Schematic diagram of circuit and equipment for recording GLH feeding on rice, IRRI.

